

#11

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING CREATING EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>When actors/stakeholders must interrogate/internalise new forms of knowledge and wish to generate ideas have been created through brainstorming.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi-actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1.5-3 hrs (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials. At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 12, 24.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- To generate group plans with clear actors/ objectives, with an added mechanism to allow reflexive decision-making.
- To facilitate participants to generate hypotheses regarding the causes of effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing.
- To facilitate participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans.

Background and Logic

Multi-actor innovation brings together a diverse range of public and private innovation actors (farmers, foresters, advisors, researchers, NGOs etc.) with complementary types and sources of knowledge to appraise, gather, co-create and disseminate practical solutions to real needs.

Multi-actor projects/initiatives require a participatory 'bottom-up approach', facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. Taking a 'bottom-up' approach to development allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation.

Interactive innovation is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach. Multi actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, where it is agreed to plan and co-design practical and implementable solutions.

This tool is inspired by [Gamble \(2018\)](#) as a reflexive tool for hypothesis building and re/generation. It is informed by a Developmental Evaluation approach where assumptions are challenged and hypotheses are revisited by adapting as the learning is carried out. Actions are connected to hypothesised results. Actual/emerging results, fact-checking and proofing is conducted using this reflexive tool. This tool allows participants to outline their goals and objectives but also allows them to continually revise and adapt their plans throughout the process.

This tool can be used with Tool#2 and Tool#12, to build hypotheses for project tasks/actions and to reflexively revise tasks/actions.

Materials

- Flipchart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Sellotape
- Pre-printed headings

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of exercise.
- Hang up all ideas previously brainstormed, which are written on sticky notes attached to flipchart paper. Note: ideas/tasks/actions may have been generated using Tool#2 or Tool#11
- Otherwise, conduct a brainstorming of ideas for tasks/actions of the project, inviting participants to write them on sticky notes and affix them to flip chart paper.

Step 2: Allocation of Ideas/Tasks/Actions

- Where Tool#2/Tool#11 was used,
 - » Revisit-reexamine the ideas/tasks/actions for the project as a reminder to participants.
 - » Each actor (working alone) team of actors (working group) is assigned its own table and ideas affixed to flipchart paper.
- Where Tool#2/Tool#11 was not used,
 - » Do a 'shopping for ideas' exercise
 - » Encourage participants to go 'shopping for ideas' where participants walk around the room and take sticky notes of previously brainstormed ideas off different flipchart sheets which contains ideas that they are interested in. Ensure sticky notes have been duplicated (or invite participants to duplicate them) for ideas that may have appealed to more than one participant.
 - » Ask participants to join together at tables where they have similar interests – these are working groups. Some actors may choose to work alone on tasks.

'Shopping for ideas'

Step 4: Formation of Group Plans

- Each working group is then handed out a piece of flipchart paper with four pre-printed headings, which are as follows:
 1. If we do.... (idea/task/action)
 2. Because.... (why?)
 3. We will get these results... (hypothesised)
 4. To achieve our goals/objectives... (impacts)

Participant/s at each table should be asked to complete each of the headings based on the ideas which they selected in the previous step. The facilitator should walk around the room engaging with each working group.

Traditional Approach (A) and a Developmental Evaluation Approach (B) (Gamble, 2018).

- At the end of the workshop, the facilitator should ask that one participant from each working group (or a single participant) presents the group plan to ensure that the entire group of participants are up to date with the plans of each individual working group. Ask that feedback is given to each group from the wider group, assisting individual groups allows them to reflect on and re-evaluate (if necessary) group plans.

Step 5: Continuous Reflexivity

As the participants continue through the process of interactive innovation, ensure that they are facilitated to continuously re-assess, update and revise group plans as required at further workshops/meetings. This encourages participants to think reflexively while also allowing participants to be in control of the decisions, adapting or revising their plans at any stage.

